

NEWSLETTER HYCOOL-IT

HYBRID COOLING & MANAGEMENT FOR IT INFRASTRUCTURES

WELCOME TO OUR HYCOOL-IT NEWSLETTER!

The Hycool-IT EU Project is working to develop a set of processes supported by both digital and technical equipment innovative solutions for an efficient and reliable development of IT Server Rooms for advanced tertiary buildings, with a special focus on its replicability through standardisation.

Let's take a look at what our project has been doing!

Since the beginning of HyCOOL-IT partners have been focused on the development and testing of the components that will conform the project proposed solutions that will be tested and installed in the pilot premises in the buildings of the Politecnico di Milano, namely i) the revamping of the Campus server room complemented by waste heat recovery for the Campus buildings and Digital Twin architecture for monitoring and control optimization trough real-time simulations and ii) the development of a novel rack-integrated adsorption chiller for efficient cooling of IT server rooms.

Revamping of the Campus server room

After completing the energy audit of Campus server room and buildings, the Power Usage Effectiveness (P.U.E.) was computed on a monthly and daily basis and the efficiency of the cooling system, the Energy Efficiency Ratio (E.E.R.), was assessed. This constituted the baseline for measuring efficiency improvements through the revamping of the Campus server room that will include new cooling equipment, waste heat recovery system to provide space heating to Campus buildings and Digital Twin architecture. Technical design and specifications for the mechanical system construction works have been completed, and the methodological framework and first simulation models for the implementation of the Digital Twin environment have been developed.

Novel rack-integrated adsorption chiller

The novel rack-integrated adsorption chiller is a solution that allows server racks to cool themselves with their own generated heat. This new adsorption chiller produces the rack's cooling effect using as driving heat source the rack's waste heat, and it is compact enough to be placed inside a commercial server rack. While researchers from the CNR-ITAE in Messina developed a preliminary model able to simulate the transient behavior of the rack-integrated adsorption chiller, Sorption Technologies obtained an initial proof of concept of this new machine. Under specific testing conditions, this first proof of concept achieved an overall cooling capacity up to 30 kW.

PROJECT NEWS

Hycool_IT second general assembly in Messina

The project team gathered in Messina last week to discuss project progress and plan next steps for the next 6 months. The design and implementation strategy has been defined based on new efficiency standards for ICT server rooms,

including recommendations for improving energy efficiency and waste heat reutilization. The strategy will address processes and requirements from use cases to contribute to innovative engineering guidelines for ICT server rooms.

[▶ Learn More](#)

Hycool_IT at Sustainable Places 2024

Hycool-IT participated for the first time in the Sustainable Places 2024 conference that was held in Luxembourg between 23 and 25 September. In a workshop titled 'From energy simulations to standards', Hycool-IT joined forces

with other EU-funded projects for the 12th annual edition of the event, these other contributors were HyperGryd, Hystore, Hybris, Senergy Nets, Dyman, Hycool-it and the BDTA.

[▶ Learn More](#)

Technical visit to pilot

On July 23rd July at Building B14a (RELAB) from the Energy department at Politecnico di Milano the Hycool-IT team met to test in situ part of the proposed solution.

[▶ Learn More](#)

Hycool_IT first general assembly in Barcelona

During the 15th and 16th April we held the first general assembly in Barcelona. As the project is at its beginnings most of the sessions were dedicated to discussing technical issues on integration of BIM, simbots, and simulations. We also carried out

discussions on simulation software and data center validation, campus energy audit and analysis. Also we talked about analysis of gas and electrical consumption and very important issue of the analysis of building energy consumption and performance assessment.

[▶ Learn More](#)

Hycool_IT kick-off meeting in Milano

The kick-off meeting for Hycool-IT was celebrated on the 13th and 14th December at Politecnico de Milano premises. During those two days work package leaders presented their general plans for the next coming months as well as held several technical discussions.

[▶ Learn More](#)

SUBSCRIBE TO OUR NEWSLETTER

Be the first to learn about project events and activities!

JOIN US !

<https://hycoolit-project.eu/>

HYCOOL-IT. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101138623